

Proteomics in ‘One Health’ approach

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The One Health approach emphasizes the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health, advocating for integrated strategies to combat health issues. Proteomics, the large-scale study of proteins, has emerged as a pivotal tool in this context, enabling comprehensive insights into the molecular mechanisms underpinning various diseases. Recent research demonstrates how proteomic analyses can uncover biomarkers for zoonotic diseases, facilitate early diagnosis, and enhance our understanding of pathogen-host interactions. Proteomics in veterinary medicine, particularly in identifying disease-related proteins in livestock, holds significant implications for food safety and public health. Furthermore, integrating proteomic data with other omics technologies (genomics, metabolomics) provides a holistic view of biological systems, fostering the development of more effective interventions. This approach also addresses the challenges in proteomic research, including the need for standardized protocols and advanced bioinformatics tools to handle complex data sets. Despite these challenges, recent advancements underscore the potential of proteomics to drive innovations in the One Health approach, ultimately contributing to the prevention and control of diseases across species and ecosystems. This interdisciplinary strategy is crucial for addressing global health challenges, emphasizing the need for continued investment in proteomic research and its applications within the One Health paradigm.

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